

Assessing the Need to Design an AI-Driven Curriculum Framework to Enhance Digital Literacy among Secondary School Science Students In Zaria, Nigeria

¹Sulaimon, H. A. PhD & ²Nuru, R.A. PhD

¹Department of Computer Science & ²Department of Biology,
Federal University of Education, Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria
sulaimonha@gmail.com

Digital literacy is a core competency for the 21st century, yet many secondary school curricula remain limited to basic ICT training and neglect critical areas, such as on-line safety, ethics, critical thinking, and adaptability to emerging technologies. Meanwhile, Artificial Intelligence offers transformative opportunities for personalized learning, adaptive content delivery and real-time feedback. This study assessed the need to design an AI-driven curriculum framework to enhance digital literacy among secondary school students. A survey approach was adopted, involving 382 students along with structured interviews of 30 teachers and expert curriculum developers and educators. Results from **SDLAIUQ** revealed inadequate digital literacy instruction, with gaps in teacher preparedness, curriculum coverage, and infrastructure. Qualitative findings reinforced these concerns, but also highlighted the enthusiasm for AI's potential, alongside issues of equity, ethics, and readiness. The study recommends for a revision of national and state curricula to embed digital literacy as a core competency, extending beyond ICT basics to include online safety, ethics, critical thinking, and responsible citizenship.

Keywords:
Digital Literacy,
Artificial
Intelligence,
Curriculum,
Secondary,
Students.

Introduction

In the twenty-first century, digital literacy emerged as a foundational competence comparable to reading, writing, and numeracy. Without adequate digital skills, individuals' risk being excluded from education, employment, and civic participation (OECD, 2024). The concept of digital literacy has evolved significantly since Glister (1997) first defined it as the ability to access and use information through digital technology. Eshet-Alkalai (2004) later described it as a survival skill for the digital era, highlighting multiple literacies: visual, reproduction, branching, information, and socio-emotional. His revised model (2012) underscores the increasing cognitive and

socio-emotional dimensions of digital engagement. Building on these foundations, Chen et al. (2020) consolidated diverse frameworks into the European Digital Competence Framework (DigComp), which outlines five key domains: information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, safety, and problem solving. Similarly, Martínez-Bravo et al. (2022) analyzed eight global frameworks and identified six common dimensions: critical, cognitive, operational, social, emotional, and projective. Over the past two decades, research has underscored the centrality of digital literacy in education and society (Shultz, 2024). Nevertheless, gaps remain in literature. For instance, Ojo et

al. (2023) and Ndibalema (2025) reports that higher education curricula in sub-Saharan Africa often fail to embed 21st-century digital skills effectively.

Artificial Intelligence has transformed educational practices. Adaptive learning systems and intelligent tutoring tools enable personalized instruction and provide targeted feedback and support. Kumar (2023) highlighted that AI-powered tools, such as Adaptive Learning Technologies and Intelligent Tutoring Systems, can significantly improve learning outcomes, although their adoption raises concerns about teacher preparedness and ethical use. Similarly, Chen et al. (2023) argued that Generative AI redefines tutoring systems by enabling real-time content creation and customized learning pathways, even as questions of accuracy and integrity persist. Despite these innovations, many school curricula continue to focus narrowly on basic ICT training, such as typing or word processing, while neglecting essential areas, such as digital ethics, media literacy, and online safety (Shultz, 2022; OECD, 2024). Teachers in Nigeria often report limited confidence in teaching advanced digital skills, which constrains students' preparedness for higher education and workforce (Odedele, et al., 2023). AI presents opportunities to address these challenges by automating assessments, delivering adaptive feedback, and generating personalized learning resources (Chen et al., 2023). Moreso, Generative AI expands opportunities for creativity, collaboration, and adaptability in the classroom (UNESCO, 2022).

By embedding AI within digital literacy curricula, schools can move beyond static ICT instruction to foster higher-order

competencies including critical thinking, ethical awareness, and responsible digital citizenship (Okoye & Onah, 2025). Such integration is essential to prepare students to thrive academically, socially, and professionally in an increasingly digital society. To ensure the proposed AI-driven curriculum framework is both sustainable and scalable, its design and implementation must explicitly integrate the **Quadruple Helix model** of innovation. This necessitates active collaboration between four key sectors: **academia, industry, government, and civil society**. This study will discuss how such synergies are essential for success. This includes partnering with **technology companies** for co-development and resource provision; engaging **government** bodies to establish supportive policy, funding, and national standards; and involving **civil society** (including communities and parents) to ensure local relevance, ethical oversight, and broader community acceptance. By adopting this multi-stakeholder approach, the framework moves beyond a theoretical academic exercise to become a practically grounded, socially responsive, and systemically supported educational innovation. This study therefore intends to determine the state of digital literacy, how AI can be used to improve digital literacy and ascertain the contents needed to develop a structured curriculum framework that integrates AI to equip secondary school students in Zaria with essential digital competencies.

Problem Statement

Although digital literacy is widely recognized as a critical competency for success in the 21st century, many high school curricula remain narrowly focused on basic ICT skills such as word processing, Internet browsing, and

office applications. Such approaches fall short of equipping students with higher-order digital competencies including critical thinking, ethical awareness, online safety, and adaptability to emerging technologies. Artificial Intelligence offers powerful opportunities to transform education. AI-driven systems can personalize learning, deliver adaptive content, and provide real-time feedback to both students and teachers. However, despite its potential, AI integration into digital literacy education remains limited, fragmented, and under researched. Schools often lack structured models that effectively leverage AI, leaving digital literacy programs inconsistent and insufficiently future-oriented. This gap highlights the urgent need for a comprehensive AI-driven curriculum framework that systematically combines digital literacy competencies with adaptive learning opportunities enabled by AI. Without such a framework, schools risk perpetuating inequalities in digital skills and leaving many students underprepared for higher education, the modern workforce, and responsible participation in digital society.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. determine the state of digital literacy education among secondary schools and identify existing gaps.
2. evaluate how artificial intelligence can be applied to improve teaching and learning digital literacy.
3. ascertain the contents needed to develop a structured curriculum framework that integrates AI to equip students with essential digital competencies.

Research Questions

The following questions are raised to guide this research:

1. What is the current state of digital literacy education in secondary schools, and what gaps exist in the curriculum?
2. How can Artificial Intelligence enhance the teaching and learning of digital literacy?
3. How can an AI-driven curriculum framework be designed to effectively prepare secondary school students with digital competencies essential for the future?

Methodology

This study adopted a survey research design that combines both quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a comprehensive understanding of how Artificial Intelligence can enhance digital literacy among secondary school students. Using a mixed approach of survey allows for triangulation of findings, thereby increasing the validity and robustness of the results. Data on students' digital literacy competencies and readiness for AI-supported learning will be determined. The qualitative component involved semi-structured interviews and expert consultations, which provided deeper insights into curriculum needs, pedagogical gaps, and the feasibility of AI integration in schools and the contents needed to develop a proposed curriculum framework. The population consisted of 62 public and private secondary schools with approximately 16,220 students, about 1,420 science teachers (Smartsrapers, 2025), and experts and curriculum developers in Zaria, as this group is directly engaged in digital literacy education and stands to benefit most from an AI-driven curriculum. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure balanced representation across school types. Six secondary schools were selected from both the public and private sectors

within the Zaria Local Government Areas. These schools included Al-Hudahuda Secondary School, Barewa College Zaria, Government Secondary School Kofar Koyambana, Zaria, Ibn Salaudeen Science Academy Zaria, Pride Academy Zaria and Aweson Academy Zaria (3 public & 3 private schools). The sample comprised approximately 382 students and 100 teachers and experts representing diverse educational contexts, ranging from resource-rich to resource-constrained environments. Students and teachers were drawn randomly.

For the survey work, 2 instruments were used to gather data. A 4-point modified -likert scale structured questionnaire titled “State of Digital Literacy and AI Utilization Questionnaire (SDLAIUQ)” which was administered to students and teachers to ascertain digital literacy and ascertain utilization of AI levels. The **Semi-Structured Interview instrument which was used to conduct**

interview with selected teachers, experts and curriculum developers to capture qualitative insights into the current state of digital literacy instruction, potential opportunities for AI integration and curriculum contents needed for a proposed curriculum. Both instruments were validated by science education experts. The study was designed and conducted in strict adherence to established ethical principles for educational research. Prior to commencement, the researchers sought permission from the Education Secretary of Zaria Local Government Authority, Zonal Education Office who in turn gave permission to visit the Quality Assurance Unit and also issued introductory letter to principals of selected schools. Data was collected across all schools within 2 weeks in June, 2025. Data collected from SDLAIUQ was analysed with mean and standard deviation statistics. The qualitative data obtained from semi-structured interviews and expert consultations were analyzed using thematic analysis as proposed by Braun & Clarke (2022).

Results

To answer the research questions, data collected were analyzed and presented as follows:

Table 1: Responses on the State of Digital Literacy in Zaria

SN	ITEM	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I feel confident evaluating the credibility of online information.	2.42	0.95	Disagree
2	The school curriculum teaches online safety and digital ethics.	2.03	0.92	Disagree
3	Students and teachers have access to devices and reliable internet	2.37	0.97	Disagree
4	Teachers receive training to integrate digital literacy and AI tools.	1.98	0.91	Disagree
5	AI tools are regularly used to support digital literacy learning	1.86	0.93	Disagree
	Cumulative mean	2.13	0.94	Disagree

The results show that the **overall mean score 2.13** indicates a **disagreement**, indicating that digital literacy education in secondary schools remained **below satisfactory levels**.

Table 2: Responses on AI Utilization level for Digital Literacy

S/N	Item	Mean	SD	Decision
1	AI utilization can personalize learning by adapting content to students' individual needs.	2.68	0.94	Utilized
2	AI-driven assessment tools provide timely and useful feedback for improving learning.	2.47	0.95	Not Utilized
3	AI utilization can reduce workload by automating routine tasks (grading, tracking).	2.41	0.96	Not Utilized
4	AI enhances engagement through interactive and adaptive learning platforms.	2.56	0.93	Utilized
5	AI tools utilization can support collaboration and creativity in digital literacy lessons.	2.48	0.95	Not Utilized
Cumulative Mean		2.52	0.95	Utilized

The results suggest cautious optimism towards AI integration in digital literacy. Respondents believe that AI can play a significant role in **personalizing instruction, engaging learners, and supporting digital literacy**, but practical barriers must be addressed for effective adoption.

Table 3: Responses on the contents needed to design an AI-Driven Curriculum Framework

S/N	Item	Mean	SD	Decision
1	An AI-driven curriculum should include modules on online safety, ethics, and responsible use.	2.58	0.92	Agree
2	The framework should integrate adaptive learning systems to personalize student learning.	2.56	0.93	Agree
3	Continuous assessment and AI-powered feedback should be part of the framework.	2.50	0.94	Agree
4	Teachers should be trained and supported to implement the AI-driven curriculum effectively.	2.58	0.91	Agree
5	The framework should align with international digital literacy standards (e.g., DigComp).	2.50	0.93	Agree
Cumulative Mean		2.54	0.93	Agree

The responses indicated strong support for the contents and design of an AI-driven curriculum framework for science students.

Furthermore, Figure 1 presents the comparison of responses from students and structured interview of teachers and experts on the content needs for designing a curriculum framework.

	 EXPERTS		
Current Practices	Limited exposure beyond basic ICT or minimal AI use	Focus mainly on typing, word processing and browsing	AI should complement, not replace teachers
Curricular Gaps	Little instruction on safety, ethics, or critical thinking	Online safety, ethics, coding, AI, and data literacy	Teacher training and capacity building essential
Teacher Preparedness	Teachers observe teachers are not trained for AI/	Uneven infrastructure across schools under-resourced	Infrastructure gaps and unequal access as critical challenges
Infrastructure	Inconsistent access to devices and internet	Limited awareness, few have heard of AI in education	Technical feasibility is high, but adoption is still early stages
Attitudes toward AI	Interested in AI for personalization and engagement	Optimistic about AI for personalization, feedback, and AI	View AI as promising but stress ethical and human-centered
Concerns	Aware of gaps but less vocal about risks	Concerned about privacy, bias, equity, and teacher replacement fears	Strong emphasis on ethics, data privacy, fairness and transparency

Fig. 1: Summary of comparison between Students, Teachers and Experts responses on designing an AI-driven curriculum framework.

Discussion

The findings in Table 1 indicate that the current state of digital literacy in Zaria’s secondary schools is low, with all items rated below the 2.50 benchmark and a cumulative mean of 2.13. Students and teachers reported limited confidence in evaluating online information, little or no exposure to online safety or digital ethics in the curriculum, inadequate access to devices and reliable Internet, and minimal teacher training or use of AI tools. These results mirror national trends, as UNICEF (2025) reported that nearly 78% of Nigerian youth lack basic digital literacy skills, while a World Bank note revealed that more than 60% of public-school teachers lack essential ICT competencies (Ndibalema, 2025; UNICEF, 2025). Similarly, Bello and Ajao (2024) emphasized that public schools suffer from resource shortages and weak teacher capacity, further widening the digital divide. Empirical evidence also shows that the availability of digital tools significantly improves students’ engagement and performance, underscoring the urgent need for investment in infrastructure and

training (Moses, 2024). Thus, the Zaria results highlight systemic gaps in digital readiness (Imoniri, 2025).

Table 2 shows that the overall AI utilization level for digital literacy in Zaria secondary schools is low to moderate (cumulative mean = 2.52). This suggests that teachers and students recognize AI’s potential benefits but lack practical exposure to its application in classrooms. Recent studies (Imoniri, 2025; UNICEF, 2025) confirm similar trends across Sub-Saharan Africa, where AI adoption in schools remains emergent due to infrastructural, pedagogical, and policy gaps. Adeoye and Musa (2024) observed that while teachers value AI for adaptive learning and interactive instruction, poor training and limited access prevent its full integration into pedagogy. Similarly, Odedele et al. (2023) highlighted that AI-based assessment and automation are rarely applied in Nigerian schools, despite their proven ability to improve feedback and reduce teacher workload in advanced contexts. Globally, scholars argue that AI is most effective when combined with strong teacher readiness and curriculum alignment (Holmes & Tuomi, 2022). Therefore, the

findings in Table 2 underscore that although there is awareness of AI's role in digital literacy, practical use remains restricted, reinforcing the need for a structured AI-driven curriculum framework and targeted teacher professional development to bridge the gap.

The results in Table 3 show a **positive consensus** on the essential components for designing an AI-driven curriculum framework, with all items scoring above the 2.50 threshold and a cumulative mean of 2.54. Respondents agreed that such a framework must embed **online safety, ethics, and responsible use** ($M = 2.58$), echoing UNESCO's (2023) emphasis on digital citizenship as a core skill for 21st-century learners. There was also strong support for integrating **adaptive learning systems** ($M = 2.56$) and **AI-powered feedback mechanisms** ($M = 2.50$), consistent with findings by Holmes and Tuomi (2022), who argue that AI can personalize instruction and enhance formative assessment when systematically embedded in pedagogy. Teacher training and professional support ($M = 2.58$) emerged as equally vital, aligning with Bello and Ajao's (2024) observation that inadequate teacher capacity remains a major barrier to digital literacy integration in Nigeria. Finally, aligning with **international digital literacy standards** such as DigComp and DQ ($M = 2.50$) reflects recognition that global benchmarks provide useful guidance for building context-sensitive, future-ready curricula (UNICEF, 2025). These findings collectively underscore that stakeholders not only acknowledge the deficiencies identified in Tables 1 and 2 but also **envision a comprehensive, structured, and standards-aligned framework** as the way forward for strengthening digital literacy in Zaria's secondary schools.

The findings in Figure 1 also provides a coherent picture of digital literacy and AI

utilization in Zaria's secondary schools. Table 1 revealed a **low baseline of digital literacy** among students and teachers, with limited confidence in evaluating information, poor access to devices and Internet, absence of online safety in the curriculum, and lack of teacher training or AI exposure. These gaps align with national reports indicating that Nigerian students and teachers have inadequate digital competencies (Odedele, et al., 2023; Bello & Ajao, 2024; UNICEF, 2025). Table 2 showed that while awareness of AI's potential benefits exists, **practical utilization remains minimal**, particularly in assessment, workload automation, and collaboration. This reflects broader challenges in AI adoption due to infrastructure and teacher preparedness deficits (Holmes & Tuomi, 2022; Imoniri, 2025). Table 3, however, highlighted a **forward-looking consensus**. Stakeholders in Africa believe an AI-driven curriculum should embed online safety, adaptive learning, AI-powered assessment, teacher professional development, and alignment with global digital literacy standards. This suggests readiness for reform and provides a roadmap for curriculum design that is both context-sensitive and internationally relevant (Afolabi, 2023; Ndibalema, 2025; UNESCO, 2023).

Conclusion

This study concludes that AI utilization in classrooms is still at an emergent stage, with most tools underutilized despite stakeholder awareness of their potential benefits. Encouragingly, respondents expressed clear support for a structured AI-driven curriculum framework that incorporates digital safety, adaptive learning systems, continuous assessment, teacher training, and alignment with international benchmarks. These findings underscore the urgent need for policy makers, curriculum developers, and

school administrators to prioritize investment in teacher professional development, ICT infrastructure, and standards-based AI integration. If implemented, the proposed framework could significantly enhance students' digital literacy, bridge equity gaps between resource-rich and resource-poor schools and better prepare Nigerian secondary school science students for participation in a global digital economy.

Recommendations

The recommendations based on the findings from the study are:

1. The Federal and Kaduna state Ministry of Education and Ministry of Science and Technology should revise the national and state curricula in use to embed digital literacy as a core competency, extending beyond ICT basics.
2. Implement continuous professional development to enhance teachers' digital and AI integration skills.
3. Teachers in Kaduna state should align curriculum reforms with global digital literacy frameworks such as DigComp.
4. Kaduna state government should encourage partnerships between government, NGOs, and private sector for resource mobilization.

References

- Adeoye, T., & Musa, H. (2024). Teachers' perceptions of artificial intelligence in enhancing digital literacy in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Journal of Digital Learning*, 14(2), 45–57.
- Afolabi, F. (2023). Digital literacy integration in Nigerian secondary schools: Challenges and prospects. *African Journal of Educational Technology*, 12(2), 45–59.
- Bello, O., & Ajao, A. O. (2024, August). Digital literacy and skills development in Nigeria:

Policies, barriers and recommendations. *Journal of African Innovation & Advanced Studies*, 5(2), 133–146.

- Braun, V. & Clarke, V. (2022). *Thematic Analysis: A Practical Guide*. <https://uk.sagepub.com>
- Chen, L., Huang, R., & Yang, J. (2023). Artificial intelligence in education: A systematic review of applications and challenges. *Computers & Education*, 194–201.
- DQ Institute (2019). Digital Intelligence (DQ) Framework. DQ Institute. www.dqinstitute.org
- Eshet-Alkalai, Y. (2004). Digital literacy: A conceptual framework for survival skills in the digital era. *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia*, 13(1), 93–106.
- Eshet-Alkalai, Y. (2012). Thinking in the digital era: A revised model for digital literacy. *Issues in Informing Science and Information Technology*, 9, 267–276.
- Glister, P. (1997). Digital literacy. New York: Wiley. <https://scrip.org>
- Holmes, W., & Tuomi, I. (2022). State of AI in education: Critical issues and policy implications. *European Journal of Education*, 57(4), 542–558.
- Imoniri, A. R. (2025). Harnessing artificial intelligence in science education for skills development and economic transformation in Nigeria. *Teacher Education and Curriculum Studies*, 10(3), 77–83.
- Kumar, K. (2023). Artificial intelligence in education: Transforming learning through adaptive technologies. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 29(3), 791–798.
- Martínez-Bravo, M. C., Sádaba Chalezquer, C., & Serrano-Puche, J. (2022). Dimensions of digital literacy in the 21st century

- competency frameworks. *Sustainability*, 14(3),1867.
- Moses, S. (2024). Impact of digital literacy skills on students' engagement and academic performance in senior secondary schools in Chikun Local Government, Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Zaria Academic Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 24(1), 76–83.
- Ndibalema, P. (2025). Digital literacy gaps in promoting 21st-century skills among students in higher education institutions in sub-Saharan Africa. *Cogent Education*, 12(1), 1-16.
- Odedele, O. F., Eze, C., & Yakubu, A. (2023). Artificial intelligence applications in Nigerian secondary schools: Opportunities and challenges. *African Journal of Educational Technology*, 6(1), 23–34.
- OECD (2024). The new ABC of tomorrow: Digital literacy as foundational as reading and arithmetic. OECD.
- Ojo, M., Adedeji, T., & Yusuf, K. (2023). Barriers to digital literacy implementation in Nigerian schools. *Journal of Digital Learning in Developing Countries*, 5(1), 21–33.
- Okoye, I., & Onah, C. (2022). Rethinking curriculum design for the digital era: Lessons for Nigerian secondary education. *International Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 14(3), 75–89.
- Shultz, M. (2024). AI in education: Opportunities, challenges, and ethical considerations. *Education and Media Digital Innovation Journal*, 2(1), 14–26.
- Smartsrapers (2025). Approximate population of secondary school students in Zaria. www.rentechdigital.com
- UNESCO. (2022). Global education monitoring report 2022: Technology in education. Paris: UNESCO Publishing. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org>
- UNESCO. (2023). Guidelines for AI competency development: Integrating ethics, safety and digital citizenship in education. Paris: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.
- UNICEF Nigeria. (2025, February 7). Connecting every child to digital learning. <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/stories/connecting-every-child-digital-learning>